

Review of Non-Isolated Inductive DC-DC Step-Up Voltage Converters for Full On-chip Integration

Róbert Ondica

*Institute of Electronics and Photonics
Slovak University of Technology
Bratislava, Slovakia
robert.ondica@stuba.sk*

Adam Hudec

*Institute of Electronics and Photonics
Slovak University of Technology
Bratislava, Slovakia
adam.hudec@stuba.sk*

David Maljar

*Institute of Electronics and Photonics
Slovak University of Technology
Bratislava, Slovakia
david.maljar@stuba.sk*

Viera Stopjaková

*Institute of Electronics and Photonics
Slovak University of Technology
Bratislava, Slovakia
viera.stopjakova@stuba.sk*

Abstract—This paper presents a summary of the commonly used inductive voltage converters (VCs) for step-up (boost) voltage conversion with their key characteristics. Many of these topologies are based on conventional Buck and Boost converters with different alterations and/or additional components. The analysis includes current conduction modes, input source and output capacitor current stresses, and the conversion ratio under Continuous Conduction Mode (CCM) operation. The selection of VCs considered in this study was guided by the feasibility of future full on-chip integration, leading to the exclusion of topologies exhibiting excessive complexity, requiring more than two inductors or need of transformers. This overview summarizes the key characteristics of the selected circuits and provides a guide for the further design of inductive voltage converters.

Index Terms—DC-DC, Voltage Converter, Conversion Ratio, PWM, PFM, CCM, DCM, ZCS, ZVS

I. INTRODUCTION

Integrated voltage converters play a pivotal role in contemporary power management systems, particularly within compact and energy-efficient electronic devices. These converters are responsible for regulating voltage levels with high precision, ensuring stable operation across a wide range of load conditions. The spread of portable, wearable, and battery-powered electronics has significantly increased the demand for miniaturized, high-efficiency power conversion solutions. Traditional discrete implementations, although functionally effective, are constrained by their relatively large form factors, higher production costs, and susceptibility to electromagnetic interference (EMI). These limitations have accelerated transition toward fully integrated power converters that can be co-fabricated with digital and analog circuitry on a single chip. Among the various topologies, inductive voltage converters are favoured for their superior energy efficiency, enhanced load regulation, and improved transient response compared to switched-capacitor (charge-pump) alternatives. However, the on-chip integration of magnetic components, particularly inductors, introduces significant challenges that

complicate the design and manufacturing processes. These challenges include limited achievable inductance due to area constraints, increased conduction losses, and parasitic effects such as substrate coupling and eddy currents. Furthermore, the quality factor of on-chip inductors is typically much lower than that of their discrete counterparts, negatively impacting overall converter performance. Addressing these issues requires advanced process technologies, innovative magnetic material engineering, and optimized circuit topologies that balance integration density with electrical performance. To address the performance limitations associated with on-chip inductors, advanced VC topologies have been developed, aiming to minimize power losses intrinsic to integrated inductors.

This paper provides an overview of inductive voltage converters, focusing on core design principles, and performance considerations. Only fundamental concepts and typical architectures are discussed, without delving into advanced modelling or specialized fabrication processes. Voltage conversion ratios are derived using the volt-second balance principle, assuming ideal components. The paper also presents common control techniques, conduction modes and switching methods that are crucial to be familiar with for efficient control of switched mode power supply. The aim is to give readers a foundational understanding of the field and highlight key considerations for further study. This introductory perspective is intended to support engineers and researchers beginning work in power converter integration.

II. CONTROLLING OF VOLTAGE CONVERTER

The approach of controlling the output voltage of the converter is necessary not only for the accurate level of the voltage to safe power delivery to the other circuits, but also for efficient power conversion and for minimizing power dissipation in the converter itself. While every topology has different requirements for safe and reliable operation, the

common operation principles are mentioned and described here.

A. Control Method

The regulation of output voltage in switched-mode power converters is achieved through the precise control of power switch timing. These converters operate by periodically altering their circuit topology, which enables the desired voltage lift. Such topological changes are implemented by switching the power switches on and off during specific intervals of the operation period. Key performance parameters of the converter – including Voltage Gain (k), Input and Output Impedances (Z_{in} , Z_{out}), and Power Conversion Efficiency (η) – are functions of the switching frequency (f_{sw}) and the duty cycle (D) of the control signal. Modulation of either of these control parameters forms the basis of the two primary voltage regulation strategies employed in switched-mode converters:

1) *Pulse Width Modulation (PWM)*: In PWM-based control, the duration of the inductor charging phase is varied in response to a monitored output variable, such as the output voltage (V_{out}) or output power (P_{out}), while the switching frequency (f_{sw}) remains constant. This modulation directly determines the duty cycle (D) of the switching signal, enabling precise regulation of the output. PWM control is particularly well-suited for applications requiring high output current. Additionally, the fixed switching frequency provides predictable electromagnetic interference (EMI) characteristics, which simplifies filter design and makes PWM widely adopted in high-power converter system [1], [2].

2) *Pulse Frequency Modulation (PFM)*: In PFM control, the turn-on time of the power switch during the charging phase is held constant, while the switching frequency (f_{sw}) is varied based on the system's load conditions. As the load increases, or when a higher voltage gain (k) is required, the control strategy increases the amount of energy transferred per unit time by increasing the switching frequency. The duty cycle (D) varies passively as a consequence of changes in the off-time. This control method is typically more efficient under light-load conditions due to reduced switching losses, as the switching frequency is generally lower than in PWM-controlled systems under similar load conditions [1].

B. Conduction Modes

Conduction modes refers to the values of the current flowing through the inductors and the current ripple during one period of the converter operation [3].

1) *Continuous Conduction Mode (CCM)*: CCM occurs when voltage converter is operated in the way that current flowing through the inductor never reaches zero. This mode is preferred because of lower current stress on the input source and/or input and output coupling capacitors [3].

2) *Boundary Conduction Mode (BCM)*: BCM is border between CCM and DCM. In this mode current through inductor drops to zero and then immediately increases [3].

3) *Discontinuous Conduction Mode (DCM)*: DCM occurs in the VC, when the current ripple in the inductor is large enough to reach zero for part of the operation period. This mode commonly occurs during light load conditions, when current needed for the load is low. Another example of DCM occurrence is use of low inductance inductor, what is common for fully integrated design. In DCM the properties of the converter change radically and converter dynamics are altered compared to CCM [3].

C. Soft Switching techniques

The transition of a power switch between its on and off states can be performed using the so-called hard switching method. This approach is typically employed when the switching events are determined solely by the timing of the control signal, without regard to the voltage or current conditions across the switch. As a result, the switch may experience non-zero voltage and current simultaneously during transitions, leading to abrupt voltage or current changes. These abrupt transitions generate surge voltages, switching noise, and significant switching losses. To mitigate these undesirable effects, soft switching techniques have been developed, which aim to reduce switching losses and electromagnetic interference by ensuring zero-voltage or zero-current conditions during switching transitions [3], [4].

Soft switching is particularly advantageous in high-frequency converters where hard switching losses become significant. By reducing switching stress, soft switching also contributes to improved thermal performance and longer device lifetimes. However, implementing soft switching increases circuit complexity and may require precise control timing. Despite this, soft switching is widely used in resonant converters, LLC converters, and other high-efficiency power supply designs [3], [4].

1) *Zero-Current Switching (ZCS)*: Zero-Current Switching is a soft switching technique where the power switch transitions from the on-state to the off-state when the current through it reaches zero, thereby reducing turn-off losses and stress due to inductive elements. This method is particularly useful for circuits where the switch is more sensitive to current during turn-off [3], [4].

2) *Zero-Voltage Switching (ZVS)*: Zero-Voltage Switching, on the other hand, ensures that the switch turns on when the voltage across it is zero, minimizing capacitive turn-on losses and improving efficiency. ZVS is commonly used in high-frequency converters to reduce switching losses and electromagnetic interference (EMI) [2]–[4].

Fig. 1: Categorization of Voltage Converters

III. NON-ISOLATED INDUCTIVE DC-DC VOLTAGE CONVERTERS FOR INCREASING VOLTAGE

The categorization of VCs is shown in the Fig. 1. VCs are firstly categorized by type of the input and output signals (AC or DC), secondly by type of controlling the power delivery (linear or switched), thirdly by type of its primary energy store device (Capacitor, Inductor or both) and lastly by their ability to increase or decrease voltage level. In this work, the emphasis is put on the converters able to lift the voltage levels – Step-Up (Boost) and Step-Up/Down (Buck-Boost) converters. The schematic of each VC topology is shown in the Figures 3 to 14.

From wide range of voltage conversion possibilities, the brief description is focused on common VCs that are suitable for full integration on the chip. Suitability for full integration heavily lies in complexity of the topology, number of used devices (especially inductors) and presence of flying capacitors and switches that requires more complex driving. Moreover, every diode in the topologies can be replaced by transistor and operated as ideal diode with zero threshold voltage to eliminate voltage drop. While eliminating power dissipation on diodes, the new challenges rises by need of intricate timing and possible employment of soft switching techniques.

A. Step-Down Converters

1) *Conventional Buck Converter*: This topology is Step-Down type of VC. It has no boost properties but the topology is shown for better understanding of connection of different Buck-Boost VCs. It consists only of one inductor (L_1), one capacitor (C_1) and one power switch (SW_1) and its topology is shown in the Fig. 2. The diode (D_1) can be realized as switch [5].

Fig. 2: Conventional Buck Converter

B. Step-Up Converters

1) *Conventional Boost Converter (CBC)*: CBC is well known and the most simple topology of voltage converter for increasing the voltage. It consists only of one inductor (L_1), one capacitor (C_1), power switch (SW_1). High-side diode (D_1) can be realized as switch. To minimize power dissipation, this switch is commonly designed as transistor and operated as ideal diode with zero threshold voltage. The advantage of this topology is absence of flying capacitors and switches, what can complicate driving circuitry.

Fig. 3: Conventional Boost Converter

2) *Double Cascaded Boost Converter (DCBC)*: DCBC is basically two CBCs connected in series, hence the topology needs twice as many devices ($L_1, L_2, C_1, C_2, SW_1, SW_2, D_1, D_2$). The benefit of this topology is increased conversion ratio with the same duty ratio. Again the High-side diodes (D_1, D_2) can be realized as switches. Low-side switches (SW_1, SW_2) must be operated in antiphase to gain voltage boost.

Fig. 4: Double Cascaded Boost Converter

3) *Non-Inverting Buck-Boost Converter (NB-BC)*: Non-Inverting Buck-Boost Converter is modification of B-BC that provides output voltage less or greater than input voltage with the same reference to the GND potential. It is essentially connection of Buck and Boost Converter in series with the shared inductor. This topology consists of one inductor (L_1), one capacitor (C_1), two power switches (SW_1 , SW_2) and two diodes (D_1 , D_2). To obtain buck or boost properties the proper control of the switches is needed. During boost mode, the switch SW_1 is constantly in conducting state and switch SW_2 controls the output voltage. During buck mode the switch SW_1 controls the output voltage and switch SW_2 is constantly in non-conducting state. This way, using only one mode, the converter is in configuration of either Conventional Boost or Conventional Buck Converter.

Fig. 5: Non-Inverting Buck-Boost Converter

4) *Split-pi Converter (S-PC)*: Split-pi Converter is buck-boost type of VC consisting of Boost and Buck converter connected in series with one capacitor in the middle. This topology again uses 2 inductors (L_1 , L_2), two capacitors (C_1 , C_2), and four power switches (SW_1 , SW_2 , SW_3 , SW_4). To obtain buck or boost properties the proper control of the switches is again needed. During boost mode the switches SW_1 and SW_2 are controlled by opposite signals, SW_3 is constantly turned on and SW_4 is constantly turned off. During buck mode the switch SW_2 is constantly turned off, SW_3 is constantly turned on and SW_3 and SW_4 are controlled by opposite signals. In buck-boost mode the switches SW_1 and SW_3 are controlled in antiphase to the switches SW_2 and SW_4 .

Fig. 6: Split-pi Converter

5) *Quadratic Boost Converter (QBC)*: QBC is converter with similar complexity as DCBC and S-PC with two inductors (L_1 , L_2), two capacitors (C_1 , C_2), one power switch

(SW_1) and three diodes (D_1 , D_2 , D_3). This topology is derived from DCBC by eliminating one active switch using Graft Scheme principle [5]. This topology, together with DCBC, has much higher k than CBC, especially for higher D .

Fig. 7: Quadratic Boost Converter

6) *Curret-Fed Bridge Converter (CFBC)*: CFBC is voltage converter based on standard bridge converter with inductor at the input. The SW_1 and SW_4 switches are driven in antiphase to SW_2 and SW_3 . The polarity of the output voltage depends on the duty cycle of control signal and is not referenced to the common ground potential.

Fig. 8: Curret-Fed Bridge Converter

C. Step-Up/Down Converters

1) *Luo Converter (Luo)*: Complexity (number and type of devices) of this converter is comparable to the SEPIC, ZC and Ćuk converter, each with different interconnections of the devices. Converter offers low output voltage and current ripple thanks to its output inductor stage. The k of this VC is at least 2.

Fig. 9: Luo Converter

2) *Buck-Boost Converter (B-BC)*: Buck-Boost Converter is modification of Buck and Boost converter that provides magnitude of output voltage greater or less than input voltage. This converter consist of the same devices as CBC (L , C , SW_1 , D_1), but the connection of devices cause output voltage to be of opposite polarity as input voltage.

Fig. 10: Buck-Boost Converter

3) *Ćuk Converter (Ćuk)*: Ćuk is another well known topology of the VC that is being employed as improved inverting Buck-Boost Converter with continuous input and output current. Its output voltage is not referenced to the ground potential and has opposite polarity as input voltage.

Fig. 11: Ćuk Converter

4) *Single-Ended Primary-Inductor Converter (SEPIC)*: SEPIC is another well known topology of the VC that provide output voltage that is greater, lower or equal to the input voltage level. It consists of series connection of Boost and Buck-Boost converter. Its main advantage is that its output drops down to 0 V when the switch is turned off, providing true shut-down with zero power consumption.

Fig. 12: Single-Ended Primary-Inductor Converter

5) *Zeta Converter (ZC)*: Zeta Converter, also known as Inverse of SEPIC Converter, is converter designed by interchanging input and output voltages of SEPIC Converter. In this configuration, the High-side switch is operated by control signal and Low-side switch can be replaced by diode.

Fig. 13: Zeta Converter

6) *Inverse Watkins-Johnson Converter (IWJC)*: This topology is base on Watkins-Johnson converter, which is buck type of VC. By inverting of this topology one can achieve alteration of k dependence on D and buck-boost properties. The polarity of the output voltage of this converter depends on the duty cycle. This converter is operated in two phases in CCM, simultaneously switching SW_1 and SW_3 opposite to the switches SW_2 and SW_4 .

Fig. 14: Inverse Watkins-Johnson Converter

IV. COMPARISON OF VOLTAGE CONVERTERS

The comparison of topologies of VCs is firstly based on complexity of the schematic, meaning number of devices and its connection. Number of inductors play crucial role especially in fully integrated circuits, where fabrication of this device presents multiple challenges. Use of flying switches (either controlled by PWM/PFM or as ideal diodes employing ZVS/ZCS methods) incur increased complexity of control circuitry, and together with flying capacitors, heightened power dissipation. Number of phases during one period of operation can further increase complexity of control circuitry, therefore increase power consumption of whole circuit. By using diodes and operating in CMM, all selected converters need only two phases during one operation period.

The character of input and output voltages and currents and its ripple can cause significant stress on power source or raise demands on input and output filter capacitors. To relax these requirements, the continuous currents and low signal ripples are preferred in wide range of applications.

Lastly, the conversion ratio k can be limiting factor of each topology in specific application. For example, it is not possible to obtain k higher than 2 with KY converter in Continuous Conduction Mode. In other cases, it can be more beneficial to implement topology with steep k characteristics (e.g. QBC,

TABLE I: Main properties of selected Non-Isolated Inductive DC-DC Step-Up and Step-Up/Down Voltage Converters

	Topology		Continuous Current	SW (flying)	D (flying)	C (flying)	L	Conversion Ratio in CCM
	Abbreviation	Name						
Step-Up Converters	CBC [3], [5]–[18]	Conventional Boost Converter	Input	1	1	1	1	$k = \frac{1}{1-D}$
	DCBC [5], [18]	Double Cascaded Boost Converter	Input	2	2 ()	2	2	$k = \frac{1}{1-D_1} \frac{1}{1-D_2}$
	NB-BC [3]	Non-Inverting Buck-Boost Converter	Input	2	2	1	1	$k = \frac{1}{1-D}$
	S-PC [19], [20]	Split-pi Converter	Both	4 ()	0	2	2	$k = \frac{1}{1-D}$
	QBC [5], [18], [21]–[23]	Quadratic Boost Converter	Input	1 ()	3 ()	2	2	$k = \frac{1}{(1-D)^2}$
	CFBC [3]	Curret-Fed Bridge Converter	Both	4 ()	0	1 (1)	1	$k = \frac{1}{2D-1}$
Step-Up/Down Converters	Luo [5], [24], [25]	Luo Converter	Output	1	1	2 (1)	2	$k = \frac{D}{1-D}$
	B-BC * [3], [5], [16], [17], [26]	Buck-Boost Step-up Converter	Output	1	1	1	1	$k = \frac{-D}{1-D}$
	Ćuk * [3], [5], [17]	Ćuk Converter	Both	1	1	2 (1)	2	$k = \frac{-D}{1-D}$
	SEPIC [3], [17], [27], [28]	Single-Ended Primary-Inductor Converter	Input	1	1	2 (1)	2	$k = \frac{D}{1-D}$
	ZC [3], [29], [30]	Zeta Converter	Output	1	1	2 (1)	2	$k = \frac{D}{1-D}$
	IWJC [3]	Inverse Watkins-Johnson Converter	Output	4 (1)	0	1	1	$k = \frac{D}{2D-1}$

* - VC with inverted output voltage polarity

DCBC) with which the same voltage gain can be achieved with lower Duty Cycle D , meaning shorter inductor charging time. Extended charging time of the inductor can mean additional conduction power losses. The dependence of k on D of each topology is shown in the Fig. 15.

The main properties of the selected Non-Isolated Inductive DC-DC Step-Up and Step-Up/Down VCs are summarized in the Tab. I. The comparison is supplemented with mathematical expression for k dependence on D in CCM, considering ideal components.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper summarizes main properties of selected VCs suitable for full integration on the chip. The emphasis is put upon inductive converters able to lift voltage level up. The input and output currents are discussed and basic complexity is shown in means of illustrations of schematics and device requirements. This overview can serve as list of essential information about characteristics of selected circuits.

In the future, the focus should be directed towards more complex hybrid VCs that offer advantages of inductive and capacitive voltage lifting techniques together, while reducing limits of use of individual types of energy storage devices. The attention should also be directed towards Discontinuous Current Conduction mode as this mode is often used in Integrated Circuits due to frequent light-load conditions and

Fig. 15: Conversion ratio of selected voltage converters

inductors with low inductance. However, this mode drastically changes dynamics of the circuit and its properties.

Lastly, different techniques to improve critical parameters of each topology could be employed. Such technique could be combination of standard topologies (such as DCBC is serial connection of two CBCs), different modification of Luo [5], [31] and other converters [23] or various advanced adjustments such as Boost cell stacking [5].

VI. ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This work was supported by Ministry of Education, Research, Development and Youth of the Slovak Republic under grants VEGA 1/0705/24 and VEGA 1/0572/25, and the Slovak Research and Development Agency under grants APVV-23-0071 and VV-MVP-24-0313. This work has also received funding from the Chips Joint Undertaking under grant agreement number 101139790 and its members, including the top-up funding by Germany, Italy, Netherlands, Slovakia and Spain.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Wens and M. Steyaert, *Design and Implementation of Fully-Integrated Inductive DC-DC Converters in Standard CMOS*. Singapore: Springer, 2011.
- [2] X. Ruan, *Soft-Switching PWM Full-Bridge Converters: Topologies, Control, and Design*. Wiley, 2014.
- [3] R. W. Erickson and D. Maksimović, *Fundamentals of Power Electronics*. Springer Cham, jan 2020.
- [4] K. S. Begum, Dharmasa, B. T. R. Rao, M. R. Reddy, and B. R. Kumar, "A study of high gain dc-dc boost converters for renewable energy sources," *International Journal of Electrical and Electronics Research (IJEER)*, vol. 12, pp. 409–414, 2024.
- [5] S. Goswami and A. Banerjee, *DC—DC Converters for Future Renewable Energy Systems*. Singapore: Springer Singapore, 1 ed., 2022.
- [6] M. Naaz, K. Fatima, B. Naik, M. Ibrahim, A. Jabeen, and S. J. Hussain, "A dc-dc boost converter using pwm with 65% efficiency," in *2023 IEEE Devices for Integrated Circuit (DevIC)*, pp. 377–382, 2023.
- [7] M. Leoncini, A. Dago, A. Bertolini, A. Gasparini, S. Levantino, and M. Ghioni, "A compact high-efficiency boost converter with time-based control, rhp zero-elimination, and tracking error compensation," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 38, no. 3, pp. 3100–3113, 2023.
- [8] J. W. Jo, D.-H. Yu, Y. Pu, Y. J. Jung, S. Kim, J.-M. Yoo, K. C. Hwang, Y. Yang, and K.-Y. Lee, "A design of boost converter with time-domain mppt and digital self-tracking zcd for thermoelectric energy harvesting applications," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 38, no. 11, pp. 14226–14235, 2023.
- [9] P.-S. Weng, H.-Y. Tang, P.-C. Ku, and L.-H. Lu, "50 mv-input batteryless boost converter for thermal energy harvesting," *IEEE Journal of Solid-State Circuits*, vol. 48, no. 4, pp. 1031–1041, 2013.
- [10] M. Alhawari, B. Mohammad, H. Saleh, and M. Ismail, "An all-digital, cmos zero current switching circuit for thermal energy harvesting," in *2015 European Conference on Circuit Theory and Design (ECCTD)*, pp. 1–4, 2015.
- [11] W.-L. Zeng, C.-W. U, and C.-S. Lam, "Review and comparison of integrated inductive-based hybrid step-up dc-dc converter under ccm," in *2019 IEEE 62nd International Midwest Symposium on Circuits and Systems (MWSCAS)*, pp. 730–733, 2019.
- [12] S.-U. Shin, Y. Huh, Y. Ju, S. Choi, C. Shin, Y.-J. Woo, M. Choi, S.-H. Park, Y.-H. Sohn, M.-W. Ko, Y. Jo, H. Han, H.-M. Lee, S.-W. Hong, W. Qu, and G.-H. Cho, "A 95.2output current delivery and low voltage ripple," in *2018 IEEE International Solid-State Circuits Conference - (ISSCC)*, pp. 430–432, 2018.
- [13] S.-U. Shin, S.-W. Hong, H.-M. Lee, and G.-H. Cho, "High-efficiency hybrid dual-path step-up dc-dc converter with continuous output-current delivery for low output voltage ripple," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 35, no. 6, pp. 6025–6038, 2020.
- [14] H. Xiong, B. Zhao, R. Yang, Z. Xie, S. Zhen, D. Ding, and B. Zhang, "A dual path hybrid step-up converter with enhanced drive voltage for low voltage applications," in *2021 IEEE 14th International Conference on ASIC (ASICON)*, pp. 1–4, 2021.
- [15] B. Zhao, H. Xiong, R. Yang, Z. Xie, S. Zhen, D. Ding, and B. Zhang, "A battery powered hybrid dual-path step-up dc-dc converter with output powered bootstrap driver," in *2021 IEEE 14th International Conference on ASIC (ASICON)*, pp. 1–4, 2021.
- [16] Y. Zhang, J. Liu, X. Ma, and J. Feng, "Comparison of conventional dc-dc converter and a family of diode-assisted dc-dc converter in renewable energy applications," *Journal of Power Electronics*, vol. 14, 03 2014.
- [17] F. Unnisa, A. Pavithra, D. V. Kumar, and K. Karunakar, "High conversion ratio sepic converter with reduced switch stress," in *2023 4th International Conference for Emerging Technology (INCET)*, pp. 1–6, 2023.
- [18] A. Balal and F. Shahabi, "Ltp spice analysis of double-inductor quadratic boost converter in comparison with quadratic boost and double cascaded boost converter," in *2021 12th International Conference on Computing Communication and Networking Technologies (ICCCNT)*, pp. 1–6, 2021.
- [19] T. Ahmad and S. Sobhan, "Performance analysis of bidirectional split-pi converter integrated with passive ripple cancelling circuit," in *2017 International Conference on Electrical, Computer and Communication Engineering (ECCE)*, pp. 433–437, 2017.
- [20] A. Alzahrani, P. Shamsi, and M. Ferdowsi, "Single and interleaved split-pi dc-dc converter," in *2017 IEEE 6th International Conference on Renewable Energy Research and Applications (ICRERA)*, pp. 995–1000, 2017.
- [21] V. K. Gupta, G. Verma, and B. C. Mandi, "Design and implementation of quadratic boost converter for low power applications," in *2024 Third International Conference on Power, Control and Computing Technologies (ICPC2T)*, pp. 415–420, 2024.
- [22] J. D. Navamani, M. L. Veena, A. Lavanya, and K. Vijayakumar, "Efficiency comparison of quadratic boost dc-dc converter in ccm and dcm," in *2015 2nd International Conference on Electronics and Communication Systems (ICECS)*, pp. 1156–1161, 2015.
- [23] H. Gholizadeh, R. S. Shahrivar, S. Amini, and T. Rahimi, "An improved cascaded boost converter with an ultra-high voltage gain suitable for dielectric quality tests," *Energies*, vol. 17, no. 15, 2024.
- [24] F. L. Luo, "Luo-converters, a series of new dc-dc step-up (boost) conversion circuits," in *Proceedings of Second International Conference on Power Electronics and Drive Systems*, vol. 2, pp. 882–888 vol.2, 1997.
- [25] Y. Jiao and F. L. Luo, "An improved sliding mode controller for positive output luo converter," in *2009 35th Annual Conference of IEEE Industrial Electronics*, pp. 195–200, 2009.
- [26] S. Miao, F. Wang, and X. Ma, "A new transformerless buck-boost converter with positive output voltage," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 63, no. 5, pp. 2965–2975, 2016.
- [27] B. K. Padhi, S. N. Padhy, and K. C. Bhuyan, "Controller design for reduced order model of sepic converter," in *2016 International Conference on Signal Processing, Communication, Power and Embedded System (SCOPES)*, pp. 1533–1538, 2016.
- [28] G. G and S. P.N, "High frequency sepic converter with pwm integral sliding mode control," in *2015 International Conference on Technological Advancements in Power and Energy (TAP Energy)*, pp. 393–397, 2015.
- [29] R. Viero, H. Lopez, C. Zollmann, and F. Reis, "Dynamic computer simulation model for a zeta converter in dcm," *XVIII Congresso Brasileiro de Automática*, pp. 3649–3654, 2010.
- [30] R. C. Viero and F. S. dos Reis, "Dynamic modeling of a zeta converter in dcm applied to low power renewable sources," in *2011 IEEE Energy Conversion Congress and Exposition*, pp. 685–691, 2011.
- [31] S. Prakash, "Comparative performance analysis of boost converter and luo converter for controllinng of dc motor speed," in *Proceedings of International Journal of Advance Research in Engineering, Science & Technology*, 04 2016.